

Synthesis and Structural Assessment of Dipseudohalidobis-(*p*-biphenyl)tin(IV) Complexes

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Dipseudohalidobis(*p*-biphenyl)tin(IV) compounds of the type $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{SnX}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{NCS}^-$, NCO^- , NCSe^- , N_3^-) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance measurements and ir spectroscopic studies. Conductivity data suggest them to be nonelectrolytes in nitrobenzene. IR spectra of the compounds suggest that NCS^- , NCO^- or NCSe^- group is N-bonded to tin atom probably forming a bridged hexacoordinated structure in the solid state.

ALTHOUGH pseudohalides of transition as well as non-transition elements of the type $\text{R}_n\text{MX}_{4-n}$ have been prepared¹⁻⁴, the nature of bonding in these derivatives has been the subject of some controversy. Amongst the various pseudohalido derivatives of organotin(IV), the isothiocyanato derivatives are most widely studied. On the basis of Mossbauer and dipole moment studies Mullins and Curran⁵ assigned a bridged polymeric structure with *trans* octahedral configuration and a hexacoordinated tin atom to $\text{R}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ compounds. The present study was undertaken to synthesise the hitherto unknown compounds of the type $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{SnX}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{NCS}^-$, NCO^- , NCSe^- or N_3^-), and to assess their structures.

Experimental

Organic solvents such as benzene, petroleum ether, methanol were purified before use following standard procedures⁶. *p*-Bromobiphenyl (Fluka), KCNS and NaN_3 (A.R., B.D.H.) were used as supplied. NaSeCN and NaCNO were prepared by literature methods⁷. Dichlorobis(*p*-biphenyl)tin(IV) was prepared by the redistribution reaction⁸ of tetra(*p*-biphenyl)tin(IV) and SnCl_4 . Tetra(*p*-biphenyl)tin(IV)^{9,10} was prepared by the following modified method.

Granular sodium (18.4 g; 0.8 mole) (prepared by dispersing sodium in xylene) was taken in benzene (~500 ml) in a three necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser, a mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel. To this a small portion of a mixture of SnCl_4 (26.07 g; 0.1 mole) and *p*-bromobiphenyl (93.2 g; 0.4 mole) was added and warmed to initiate the reaction. The remaining portion of the mixture was then added dropwise with constant stirring over 30 min. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 5 hr and filtered hot. On cooling, tetra(*p*-biphenyl)tin was obtained as a white powder, yield ~65 g (~90%).

Preparation of $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$:

A solution of $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ (0.495 g; 1 m mole) in acetone (~30 ml) was added to a solution of anhydrous KSCN (0.194 g; 2 m mole) in methanol (~60 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr and then filtered to remove KCl. The filtrate was concentrated (~15 ml) under reduced pressure and petroleum ether (60-80°) was added dropwise to precipitate the product. Dirty white product was obtained in ~80% yield. Other pseudohalido derivatives were prepared by analogous methods.

Physical measurements :

C and H were determined microanalytically and Sn as SnO_2 gravimetrically. Elico conductivity bridge, CM82T, was used for molar conductance measurements. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer model-621 grating spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

The pseudohalido derivatives have been prepared by refluxing sodium/potassium pseudohalide with $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ in a mixture of acetone and methanol.

The compounds are white crystalline solids having sharp melting points. The azido compound does not melt upto 300°. The compounds are fairly soluble in polar organic solvents, comparatively less soluble in nonpolar solvent and insoluble in water. They are stable at room temp in the absence of moisture. The results of conductivity measurements indicate that the compounds are nonelectrolytic in nature.

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA FOR R_2SnX_2

Compound	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Molar conductance	
		Carbon	Hydrogen	Tin	$\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$	Molarity (mM)
R_2Sn	260	79.1 (78.8)	4.5 (4.9)	16.6 (16.2)	—	—
$R_2Sn(NCS)_2$	230	57.9 (57.7)	3.6 (3.3)	22.2 (21.9)	0.71	0.5
$R_2Sn(NCO)_2$	270	61.1 (61.3)	3.4 (3.5)	23.5 (23.3)	0.68	0.5
$R_2Sn(NCSe)_2$	220	48.9 (49.1)	2.5 (2.8)	—	0.58	0.5
$R_2Sn(N_3)_2$	>300	56.8 (56.6)	3.8 (3.5)	23.0 (23.3)	0.82	0.5

$R = (p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$

Vibrational spectroscopic studies :

Triatomic pseudohalogen groups generally exhibit three vibrational fundamentals¹, viz., asymmetric, symmetric stretching vibrations and a deformation mode. While the asymmetric mode varies a little from one pseudohalide to the other, the latter two depend largely on the nature of the pseudohalogen group. In coordination compounds the CNX group (X=S, O or Se) may coordinate to metal atom through either N or X.

In thiocyanato compound it was shown¹¹ that $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ mode occurs at a lower wave number in $\text{M}-\text{NCS}$ than in $\text{M}-\text{SCN}$ derivatives. Moreover, the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ frequency is higher ($860\text{-}780\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in N-bonded than in S-bonded ($720\text{-}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹²⁻¹⁴ compounds. It was further suggested^{12,14} that N-bonded compounds exhibit a single sharp (NCS) bending mode at $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas the S-bonded compounds show several bands of low intensity at $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Present investigation reveals that the thiocyanato group is primarily bonded to tin atom through nitrogen, thus assuming an *iso* structure, and that the compound has bridged structure with bridging through sulphur in the solid state.

These conclusions have been drawn on the basis of the presence of one strong band below 2100, one band between 490-460, and absence of any band in the $720\text{-}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. An additional weak band at $\sim 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is proposed for partial bridging^{15,16}. From the bands present in the $860\text{-}780\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, it is rather difficult to get any clue because of masking by other absorptions i.e. (C-H) out of plane bending, etc.¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

As regards the cyanato compound, the normal metal cyanates²⁰ exhibit $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ below 1200 cm^{-1} , while metal isocyanates²¹ does at around 1400 cm^{-1} . The compound $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCO})_2$ shows one band at 1380 cm^{-1} thereby presenting an example of a true isocyanato compound.

Tin possesses d-orbitals available for $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding with the spare electrons on N, and thus leads to structure such as $\text{M}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{N}^- = \text{C} = \text{O}$, similar to that predicted for $\text{Si}(\text{NCO})_4^{22}$. Such structures

require the $\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{O}$ group to be essentially linear²³ for a true tetrahedral molecule. With the evidence available we cannot say definitely whether the NCO in the present case is linear. The presence of two or more bands in the $620\text{-}590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, however, suggests the possibility of partial bridging through oxygen atom⁴.

Metal and organometal selenocyanates are comparatively less studied compounds. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ generally falls below 2080 cm^{-1} for N-bonded and above for Se-bonded compounds²⁴ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Se})$ lies in the $700\text{-}620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region for $\text{M}-\text{NCSe}$ and the $550\text{-}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region for $\text{M}-\text{SeCN}$. Similarly, $\nu(\text{NCSe})$ occurs at 400 cm^{-1} for $\text{M}-\text{NCSe}$. In the compound $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCSe})_2$, a broad band between $2060\text{-}2020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a single band at 700 cm^{-1} suggest N-bonded (NCSe) group to tin, which is also supported by the absorption at 420 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{NCSe})$.

The azide group in various organometallic compounds of group IVA (Si, Ge, Sn and Pb) have been characterized on the basis of the vibrations^{25,26} (i) $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{NNN})$ at ~ 2100 , (ii) $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NNN})$ at ~ 1300 and (iii) $\nu(\text{NNN})$ at 660 cm^{-1} . In the present compound strong bands at 2050, 1360 and 610 cm^{-1} indicate the occurrence of azide group. As the spectrum is similar to other metal azides²⁷, an ionic bonding between tin and azide group may be suggested.

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